

An overview of publishers' guidelines for sharing research data

Date: 2025-03-17

Version: 1

[Creative Commons Attribution 4.0](#)
(CC-BY 4.0)

Swedish National Data Service

snd.se

(+46) 31-786 10 00

snd@snd.se

SND, University of Gothenburg,

Box 468, 405 30 Gothenburg, Sweden

Summary

This report provides an overview of the research data sharing policies of the world's largest academic publishers: Elsevier, Springer Nature, Wiley, MDPI AG, and Taylor & Francis. It collates the publishers' requirements and recommendations and identifies key differences between the publishers' policies.

The main findings of the review are:

- All the reviewed publishers encourage or require data sharing, but there are variations in how strict their requirements are. Most policies are based on voluntary data sharing, but some publishers require open data sharing for specific types of research data (e.g., genetic data at Springer Nature). Wiley and Taylor & Francis have developed tiered data sharing policy levels to offer more flexibility to researchers and journals. These levels range from encouragement to mandatory peer review of shared data.
- The publishers require “Data Availability Statements” (DAS), where researchers must disclose how their data can be accessed. These are mandatory for Springer Nature, Wiley, MDPI AG, and the majority of Taylor & Francis journals, while Elsevier only encourages providing a DAS.
- All publishers recommend publishing data in digital repositories, but they rarely specify which repositories should be used and they are generally open to data being shared in other ways too. Most publishers recommend applying the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), although there is rarely any information on how compliance is monitored. Elsevier has its own list of ten criteria for data management, while MDPI AG also refers to the TOP guidelines for open science.

The review found that the major scientific publishers have all established data sharing policies, encouraging – and in some cases requiring – researchers to make their data accessible. However, knowledge gaps remain. It is unclear how compliance with the publishers' rules is monitored in practice. Moreover, there is a clear tension between openness and the need for restrictions due to ethical, legal, and commercial considerations. It is not known how researchers in different disciplines are responding to the publishers' various data sharing policies.

The knowledge gap

Publishing articles in academic journals is the primary path by which researchers share their findings and contribute to the scientific body of knowledge. Access to these research results has increased significantly over the past decade, and in 2023, 77% of all peer-reviewed articles from Sweden were open access immediately on publication (Kungliga Biblioteket, 2024). The increased accessibility of scientific articles has not, however, been matched by an increase in the accessibility of the underlying research data. Sharing of research data is increasingly encouraged and is sometimes required, for example by research funders. However, making research data openly accessible remains a challenge in many fields of research, and the extent of data sharing varies widely between disciplines and traditions.

Many academic publishers have begun implementing data sharing policies, where researchers are encouraged – or in some cases required – to make their data available. These policies play a key role in increasing the credibility of research by promoting research transparency and enabling replication.

The purpose of this document is to map out the data sharing policies of major academic publishers. The following questions further specify this aim:

- What are the publishers' overarching policies for sharing research data?
- What requirements do the publishers place on data sharing?
- What are the publishers' expectations regarding the quality or accessibility of the data?
- How should the data be shared?

Method

This review focuses on the five largest publishers globally in terms of the number of published articles. Together, these publishers are responsible for more than 10,000 journals that publish around 2 million articles annually. These publishers, listed in order of the number of articles published, are Elsevier, Springer Nature, Wiley, MDPI AG, and Taylor & Francis (Scilit, 2024).

Publisher	Data sharing policies
Elsevier	https://www.elsevier.com/about/policies-and-standards/research-data
Springer Nature	https://www.springernature.com/gp/authors/research-data-policy
Wiley	https://authorservices.wiley.com/author-resources/Journal-Authors/open-access/data-sharing-citation/index.html
MDPI AG	https://www.mdpi.com/ethics#_bookmark21
Taylor & Francis	https://authorservices.taylorandfrancis.com/data-sharing-policies/

The findings in this review are based on information provided by the publishers about their data sharing policies on their respective websites. Links to each of the publishers' main pages on data sharing are listed in the table above. In addition to these pages, the results in this review also draw on detailed information from subpages accessed from the main pages.

Results

General data sharing policies

All publishers included in this review present guidelines on whether and to what extent researchers should share their data, using terms such as “research data policy” and “data sharing policy.” Overall, the publishers encourage or strongly encourage researchers to share their data openly. However, the general policies of the publishers typically do not mandate open data sharing. There are two types of exceptions to this. First, two publishers define different levels of standardized policies that their journals can choose from (see separate section below), and some of these levels go beyond mere encouragement. Second, Springer Nature requires that certain types of data (e.g., DNA sequence data, genetic variation data, protein sequence data) must be deposited in a public data repository when publishing in their journals.

Even though the publishers' general policies do not mandate open data sharing, none of the publishers explicitly oppose that their journals adopt stricter requirements. Elsevier even states that some of its journals – particularly in disciplines where the good research practice includes data sharing – are allowed to implement policies for mandatory data archiving and sharing. Furthermore, Taylor & Francis emphasize the importance of checking whether research funders have data sharing policies, and notes that if there is a conflict between the funders' and the publisher's policies, the policy prescribing more extensive data sharing should be followed.

All publishers included in this review state in their guidelines that some data cannot or should not be shared openly. Although the publishers differ in how thoroughly they address exceptions to data sharing, the overarching reasons consistently relate to ethical, legal, or security concerns. For example, Taylor & Francis lists six exceptions to data sharing:

1. when data sharing conflicts with personal data protection;
2. when the researcher does not own the data;
3. when data are commercially sensitive or protected by competition laws or market regulation;
4. when data release poses a security risk;
5. data which are under consideration in any legal actions;
6. when sharing could threaten protected species.

In such cases, several publishers encourage researchers to take steps to share as much data as possible, as openly as possible, rather than refraining from sharing entirely. Springer lists the following examples of such approaches:

- Anonymizing data to create a shareable version.
- Use of a controlled-access repository to manage who can access data and under what terms.
- Use of Trusted Research Environments or data safe havens.
- Creating metadata records in repositories for data that cannot be publicly shared.

All publishers emphasize the importance of sharing research data as openly as possible. Elsevier and Taylor & Francis are the most explicit in their encouragement, both highlighting that sharing research data provides benefits for (1) the researchers themselves, (2) the research community, and (3) society at large. The benefits for individual researchers include receiving recognition for their work, gaining more citations (Colavizza et al., 2020), and increasing visibility that may lead to new collaborations. The research community also benefits through increased transparency and opportunities for validation, easier reuse and replication of research, and less wasted resources. Finally, for society at large, benefits include strengthening public trust in research and improving research accessibility.

Data Availability Statements

All publishers provide guidelines on whether and how researchers should disclose the availability of the data underlying their studies. The publishers consistently describe such disclosure using the term *Data Availability Statement* (DAS). For journals affiliated with Springer Nature, Wiley, and MDPI AG, it is mandatory to include a Data Availability Statement, while Elsevier and Taylor & Francis merely encourage researchers to do so. However, for Taylor & Francis journals that have their own specific data sharing policies – which includes most of their journals – it is mandatory to include a Data Availability Statement.

Except for Elsevier, the publishers provide detailed information on what should be included in a Data Availability Statement and offer recommended phrases that depend on the level of data availability. Below are example phrases from MDPI AG, but similar examples are presented by Springer Nature, Wiley, and Taylor & Francis:

Level of availability	Example wording
Data available in a publicly accessible repository	The original data presented in the study are openly available in [repository name, e.g., FigShare] at [DOI/URL] or [reference/accession number].
Data available on request due to restrictions (e.g., privacy, legal or ethical reasons)	The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author due to (specify the reason for the restriction).

3rd party data	Restrictions apply to the availability of these data. Data were obtained from [third party] and are available [from the authors/at URL] with the permission of [third party].
Dataset available on request from the authors	The raw data supporting the conclusions of this article will be made available by the authors on request.
Embargo on data due to commercial restrictions	The data that support the findings will be available in [repository name] at [URL / DOI link] following an embargo from the date of publication to allow for commercialization of research findings.

No publisher requires researchers to use the exact wording from the examples they provide, but two of them – Wiley and MDPI AG – go further by explicitly encouraging or recommending the use of the suggested phrases. Springer Nature differs from the other publishers by offering different example statements tailored to specific research disciplines: (1) life sciences and clinical medicine, (2) chemistry and chemical biology, (3) physics, and (4) humanities and social sciences. When data are to be shared via a repository, the publishers state that a DOI or another persistent identifier should be included.

Data accessibility

In addition to general guidelines on whether and to what extent researchers should share their data, the publishers also provide recommendations on data accessibility.

Three of the publishers – Wiley, MDPI AG, and Taylor & Francis – explicitly recommend the use of the FAIR principles, meaning that data should be *Findable*, *Accessible*, *Interoperable*, and *Reusable*, as outlined in Wilkinson et al. (2016). It is worth noting that the use of the FAIR principles is generally presented as a recommendation. The exception is the Taylor & Francis journals, which adopt the publisher’s most stringent data availability guidelines (see separate section below), that require that data comply with the FAIR principles.

As for the two other publishers, Springer Nature provides a less-detailed description, while Elsevier outlines ten characteristics that define high-quality data: (1) stored, (2) preserved, (3) accessible, (4) discoverable, (5) citable, (6) comprehensible, (7) reviewed, (8) reproducible, (9) reusable, and (10) integrated. Elsevier’s ten characteristics align closely with the FAIR principles, with the main difference being the seventh characteristic; that research data, like research articles, should be peer-reviewed. Although Elsevier emphasizes its own ten characteristics rather than the FAIR principles, it highlights its role as a co-author of the FAIR principles and as a founding member of FORCE11 (2025), an organization dedicated to promoting and disseminating these principles.

The three publishers that explicitly recommend the FAIR principles – Wiley, MDPI AG, and Taylor & Francis – do not provide detailed explanations of the principles or guidance on how researchers

should implement them. Like Elsevier, Wiley and Taylor & Francis refer to FORCE11, where the FAIR principles are explained in more detail. MDPI AG, for its part, states that its data policy is based on the TOP Guidelines (Center for Open Science, 2025). Like the FAIR principles, the TOP Guidelines aim to promote openness and transparency in research. The TOP guidelines are broader in scope, however, including recommendations such as study preregistration and encouragement of replication studies.

Regardless of whether they refer to the FAIR principles (Wiley, MDPI AG, and Taylor & Francis), the TOP Guidelines (MDPI AG), or Elsevier's own ten characteristics, it is not clear whether the publishers or their journals actually verify that shared research data meet the recommended principles or criteria.

Data repositories

When it comes to how data should be shared, all the reviewed publishers recommend that researchers use a repository. However, it should be noted that the publishers are open to data being shared in other ways – for example, by providing data upon request directly from the author(s). In some cases – such as for certain data types at Springer Nature, or for certain levels of policy at Wiley and Taylor & Francis (see separate section below) – the publishers *require* researchers to use a repository. Springer Nature also states that a growing number of their journals now require researchers to share data through repositories, even though the publisher does not generally seem to enforce this.

None of the publishers require that researchers use specific repositories, with the exception that Springer Nature specifies particular repositories for protein sequence data and proteomics data. The following is a closer look at each publisher's recommendations regarding repositories:

Elsevier offers its own option in the form of *Mendeley Data* (2025), which is free for researchers to use. Mendeley Data supports the FAIR principles, assigns a DOI to each dataset, and supports a wide range of file formats – from various text formats (e.g., .txt, .pdf) to different GIS formats (e.g., .gml, .mif). Elsevier imposes certain requirements for data shared via Mendeley Data, such as requiring a dataset description and disallowing previously published data. These criteria are verified before publication. Researchers publishing with Elsevier journals are, however, free to choose other repositories, including – but not limited to – the 60+ repositories with which Elsevier has partnerships.

Springer Nature, as mentioned above, do require that specific repositories are used for a few types of data, but in most cases, there is considerable flexibility. The publisher's general policy is that data should preferably be shared via recognized subject-specific repositories and via general repositories only if no suitable subject-specific option exists. Springer Nature provides examples of subject-specific repositories in the following areas: (1) biology, (2) chemistry and chemical biology, (3) earth, environmental, and space sciences, (4) health sciences, (5) materials science, (6) physics, and (7) social sciences. For general repositories, six options are mentioned, including the *Dryad Digital*

Repository (2025) and *figshare* (2025). An important point for researchers publishing in Springer Nature journals is to check each journal's specific policy, as some have their own preferred repositories.

Wiley provides relatively limited information on repository selection. Like Springer Nature, Wiley's general guidance is that data should be shared via recognized subject-specific repositories but that they may be shared via general repositories if no suitable subject-specific option is available. Wiley advises researchers to consult specific journals' and funders' policies. To find appropriate, registered, and certified subject-specific repositories, Wiley refers researchers to *re3data* (2025) and *FAIRsharing* (2025). Although researchers are free to select suitable repositories, Wiley has a partnership with the *Dryad Digital Repository* (2025), and some Wiley journals cover the data publication fees for Dryad.

MDPI AG also provides limited information on repository selection. However, the publisher outlines a few criteria that researchers should consider when selecting a repository: (1) it must ensure long-term preservation and accessibility, (2) it must provide persistent identifiers, (3) it must allow unrestricted open access, (4) it must support open licenses (e.g., CC0, CC-BY), and (5) it must offer confidential peer review of data. Any repository that meets these criteria to a sufficient extent is acceptable. Like Wiley, MDPI AG generally recommends using *re3data* (2025) and *FAIRsharing* (2025) to find registered and certified subject-specific repositories.

Taylor & Francis recommends that researchers follow a three-step checklist. First, researchers should review the specific journal's instructions to see what data sharing policies apply and whether any repositories are recommended. Second, the publisher advises contacting institutional data specialists, such as librarians. If a repository still has not been identified, Taylor & Francis – like Wiley and MDPI AG – recommends using *re3data* (2025) or *FAIRsharing* (2025) to locate relevant subject-specific repositories. If no suitable subject-specific repository is found, the publisher lists about ten general-purpose repositories, including *Dryad Digital Repository* (2025) and *Mendeley Data* (2025). Additionally, Taylor & Francis supports *ScholarXplorer* (2025), which facilitates linking published articles to associated datasets. If data are deposited in a ScholarXplorer-recognized repository, a link to the dataset is automatically created on the article's webpage, making it easier to access the data.

Standardized data sharing policies

Two of the publishers – Wiley and Taylor & Francis – offer suites of standardized data sharing policies that their journals can adopt in order to facilitate the process of making research data available. While the exact number and naming of the levels vary, they share similar structures: ranging from basic encouragement to stricter requirements for openness, and in some cases, peer review of the data.

Wiley's Policy Levels

Wiley offers data sharing policies in four levels:

1. Encourages data sharing
2. Expects data sharing
3. Requires data sharing
4. Requires data sharing and peer reviews data

On Wiley's website, researchers can use an *Author Compliance Tool* to quickly check which policy level applies to a specific journal.

Journals that (1) *encourage data sharing* encourage authors to share data and other materials supporting the results in their articles by depositing them in a public repository. Authors may include a Data Availability Statement in their article with a link to the repository, and shared data should be cited. All accepted manuscripts can include a statement indicating whether data have been shared or not. If data are shared, the statement should describe how they can be accessed and provide a persistent identifier (e.g., DOI or accession number).

Journals that (2) *expect data sharing* expect that data supporting the results in an article will be deposited in a public repository. Authors must include a Data Availability Statement describing the availability – or lack of it – of shared data. If data are shared, the statement must include a repository link, and data should be cited. When possible, scripts and other materials used for the analysis should also be archived publicly. If authors are unable to share data (for example, because of ethical standards or legal requirements), then sharing is not required and authors must describe the restrictions in their Data Availability Statement.

Journals that (3) *require data sharing* require that data supporting the article's results must be deposited in a public repository as a condition for publication. Authors must include a Data Availability Statement with a repository link and cite the shared data. When possible, scripts and other analytical materials should be archived publicly. Exceptions may be granted by the editor, for instance, if data sharing would compromise individual privacy, ethical standards, or legal requirements. If authors cannot share data, they must justify this in the Data Availability Statement.

Finally, journals may adopt policy (4) *requiring data sharing and peer reviews data*. This means the journal requires that data supporting the article's results undergo peer review and be deposited in a public repository as a condition of publication. Authors must provide a Data Availability Statement with a repository link and cite the data. When possible, scripts and other materials used in the analysis should also be made publicly available. Exceptions may be granted by the editor, for example, when data sharing would conflict with ethical standards or legal obligations. In addition, one of the following conditions must be verified through peer review of the empirical data, either that:

1. the quality of the data is verified, for example by checking that sample sizes match, that the variables described in the article are present as fields in the data repository, that data are complete, properly labelled, and include relevant metadata, or

2. that the data reproduce the analytical results reported in the article.

In conclusion, although the third and fourth policy levels are phrased as “requiring data sharing,” journal editors retain the discretion to grant exceptions. Based on Wiley’s brief descriptions of this, it appears that the publisher does not provide detailed criteria for what constitutes acceptable grounds for exception, leaving such decisions to the judgment of individual editors.

Taylor & Francis Policy Levels

Taylor & Francis provide five levels of data sharing policies:

1. Basic data sharing policy
2. Share upon reasonable request
3. Publicly available
4. Open data
5. Open and FAIR

Journals that adopt the *basic data sharing policy* should encourage authors to share data and other materials that support the findings in their articles by depositing them in a recognized repository. Authors may include a Data Availability Statement in their article with information on how the data can be accessed and cited. Data should be shared when it is ethically sound and does not violate confidentiality or privacy requirements.

Journals that adopt the *share upon reasonable request* policy expect authors to make data available to others upon reasonable request. The author determines what constitutes a reasonable request. It is recommended that data be deposited in a repository prior to publication to facilitate future sharing. A Data Availability Statement describing the access conditions or any limitations to data sharing must be included in the article.

Journals that adopt the *publicly available* policy require that data supporting the article’s findings be deposited in a public repository and made available to all. However, authors may apply a license that limits reuse of the data. A Data Availability Statement should be included with a link to the repository, and the shared data must be cited. For this and the following policies, authors are asked to provide a DOI or similar at the point of submission.

Journals that adopt the *open data* policy require that data be freely available under a licence (e.g., CC-BY or CC0) that allows reuse for any lawful purpose. Authors must ensure that data are findable, accessible, and accompanied by relevant metadata. A Data Availability Statement must be provided – preferably at article submission – which must describe how the data can be accessed, and the data must also be cited.

Finally, journals that adopt the *open and FAIR* policy impose the same requirements as for open data, but the data must also comply with the FAIR principles. This means the data must follow established standards within the relevant research field and be deposited in a repository that supports long-term preservation and assigns a persistent identifier (e.g., DOI).

For all levels, authors are expected to include a Data Availability Statement in their article and cite the data in accordance with Taylor & Francis’s guidelines for proper citation practices. Exceptions to data sharing may be granted by the editor if data sharing would conflict with ethical standards, confidentiality, or legal obligations.

Conclusion and Outlook

This review has found that all of the major scientific publishers have established data sharing policies, with researchers increasingly encouraged – and in some cases required – to make their data accessible. Although the publishers’ general policies are primarily based on voluntary participation, there are clear differences between them in terms of how far-reaching the requirements are and to what extent individual journals within each publisher are allowed to tailor their own guidelines. Particularly noteworthy is that some publishers, such as Wiley and Taylor & Francis, have introduced standardized levels of data sharing, providing clarity and flexibility for both researchers and journal editors.

	Data sharing policy	Data Availability Statement	Data accessibility	Data sharing
Elsevier	Yes	Encouraged	Own criteria & FAIR	Repository (Mendeley Data)
Springer Nature	Yes	Required	No explicit guidelines	Repository (subject-specific preferred)
Wiley	Yes	Required	FAIR	Repository (subject-specific preferred)
MDPI AG	Yes	Required	FAIR, TOP	Repository (subject-specific preferred)
Taylor & Francis	Yes	Encouraged/Required	FAIR	Repository (subject-specific preferred)

The review also highlights ongoing challenges and limitations. Although principles such as FAIR and TOP are frequently referenced, there is little clarity on how compliance is assessed in practice. A deeper analysis of how journals in different fields interpret and implement their publisher’s guidelines would be a valuable follow-up.

This review is based on publicly available information from publishers' websites, and clear answers to some questions were hard to find. It may therefore be helpful to contact publishers directly to clarify how compliance with data sharing policies is monitored, and whether responsibility lies with journal editors, with the publishers themselves, or if no formal oversight exists at all.

There is also a clear tension between the ambition to maximize openness and the need to manage ethical, legal, and commercial restrictions. We have limited insight into how often researchers are actually granted exemptions from data sharing. A targeted analysis to produce statistics on how frequently such exemptions occur – and on what grounds – would provide objective information on how these competing demands are handled in practice.

Stricter guidelines on data publication are also likely to influence researchers' choice of journal. Understanding how researchers in different disciplines respond to data sharing requirements and what challenges they face is therefore an important area for investigation. Such a study could serve as a foundation for developing guidance or training materials to help researchers navigate the diverse policies of different publishers.

Looking ahead, we can expect data sharing policies to continue evolving, especially as research funders and academic institutions impose stronger requirements for open science. One possible development is that more publishers will implement stricter data sharing mandates, either through broader adoption of compulsory policies or through increased use of data review during the publication process. It would also be valuable to explore how publishers themselves view future requirements for data sharing, and whether they see themselves as drivers of such developments, and if so, in what direction.

References

Publisher's homepages

Elsevier

<https://www.elsevier.com/about/policies-and-standards/research-data>

Springer Nature

<https://www.springernature.com/gp/authors/research-data-policy>

Wiley

<https://authorservices.wiley.com/author-resources/Journal-Authors/open-access/data-sharing-citation/index.html>

MDPI AG

https://www.mdpi.com/ethics#_bookmark21

Taylor & Francis

<https://authorservices.taylorandfrancis.com/data-sharing-policies/>

Other references

Center for Open Science. (2025). *Top Guidelines*. <https://www.cos.io/initiatives/top-guidelines>

Colavizza, C., Hrynaszkiewicz, I., Staden, I., Whitaker, K., & McGillivray, B. (2020). The citation advantage of linking publications to research data. *PLOS One*, 15(4), Artikel e0230416.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0230416>

Dryad Digital Repository. (2025). *Dryad*. <https://datadryad.org/>

FAIRsharing. (2025). *FAIRsharing.org: standards, databases, policies*. <https://fairsharing.org/>

figshare. (2025). *figshare*. <https://figshare.com/>

Force11. (2025). *Force11: The Future of Research Communications and e-Scholarship*.

<https://force11.org/>

KB. (2024). *Öppen tillgång i siffror*. <https://www.kb.se/samverkan-och-utveckling/oppen-tillgang-och-bibsamkonsortiet/oppen-tillgang/oppen-tillgang-i-siffror.html>

Mendeley Data. (2025). Share your research data. <https://data.mendeley.com/>

re3data. (2025). *re3data.org: Registry of Research Data Repositories*. <https://www.re3data.org/>

ScholarXplorer. (2025). Scholarly Literature & Data interlinking <https://scholarxplorer.openaire.eu/>

Scilit. (2024). *Publishers Ranking*. <https://www.scilit.net/rankings/publishers?year=2024&rows=100>

Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., ... & Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship.

Scientific Data, 3(1), Artikel 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>